

Simulation of the electromechanical model of a doubly-fed induction generator wind turbine using an NVIDIA GPU

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Abstract

Parallel simulation techniques have become a great tool to overcome studies where a large demand of computational effort is needed. One of these cases is the integration of renewable energy in power systems, such as the wind energy. In this paper, it is proposed a highly parallel solver for the simulation of a large number of wind turbines equipped with a doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG), coded using the NVIDIA's CUDA architecture, based on NVIDIA graphic processing units (GPUs). The implementation involves the solution of a linearized time-invariant system in state space form, where both 5th and 3rd order representations of the wind turbine model are considered. These models have also been implemented in Simulink and C++ to compare the computational cost against the CUDA implementation, modifying the number of wind turbines simulated. Results show that the CUDA implementation is up to 15 times faster than the C++ implementation.

Key words: DFIG, Wind turbine, parallel programming, SIMULINK, C++, CUDA

1. Introduction

Worldwide electric energy consumption is steadily increasing, and more power plants are being planned to meet this need. Many countries have opted to use wind energy not only for covering the new demand, but also to substitute classical power generation, which is mainly based on coal, [1]. When new generation units are installed in the electrical grid, simulations of the state of the network must be carried out to ensure the stability of the power system. Transport System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs) face the challenge of adding wind turbine models on their existing network models. Its unpredictability and sheer number of generators make the computation of the state of the grid is computationally expensive, [2]. Aggregate models have been used to model the output of a wind farm to reduce the computation cost, but this reduction implies ignoring details of the individual behaviour of every wind turbine of the wind farm, [3]. Therefore, building highly parallel computing solutions for simulating power systems with a high number of wind turbines seems to be a very good option to overcome these issues.

The wind turbine considered in this work is equipped with a DFIG where the stator is connected directly to the grid, while the rotor terminals are connected through a back-to-back converter rated to 25-30% of the generator nominal power value [5].

Computing processing power has consistently raised as predicted by “Moore’s law” [4], although it is expected to end this increase due to limitations imposed by physics. If raw speed does not increase, parallelism is the way to simulate higher and more complex systems and this is the scenario where graphic processing cards have shown its potential. Those are called GPUs; devoted coprocessors originally designed to alleviate the central processing unit (CPU) from doing the graphics processing. In particular, NVIDIA has developed the Compute Unified Device Architecture “CUDA” which allows seamless integration of code executed in their graphics card and code executed in the CPU. CUDA will allow the creation of massive parallel solvers of wind turbine models, largely faster than the usual C++ implementations.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly describes the non-linear model used to represent a DFIG wind turbine model. Section 3 introduces the linearization method to convert the original equations into a linear time invariant (LTI) system in the state space form. Section 4 shows how the MATLAB-Simulink, [6], wind turbine model has been implemented. Section 5 describes the C++ solver for the LTI system. Section 6 explains the CUDA implementation and the considerations taken to optimize it. Section 7 shows the experimental results. Finally, conclusions are detailed in Section 8.

2. DFIG wind turbine model

The DFIG wind turbine model is composed by a set of equations that have been obtained from [7], in this section a brief presentation will be given so for further detailed explanation the reader is referred to [7]. It has been modelled using the $dq0$ transformation, resulting in a simpler, easier to control system, [8]. In Figure 1, the electrical equivalent circuit of the generator is shown. To strengthen mathematical stability and further simplify equations, per unit systems were used.

Figure 1. Equivalent circuit of the induction generator

The wind turbine system is considered balanced so the omission of the 0 component is correct. Two sets of models of the generator are considered. The 5th order model represents accurately all dynamics present in the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 1, whereas the 3rd order model simplifies the equations, removing the stator flux as a state variable, [9]. This simplification implies neglecting stator fast transients, allowing for a greater integration step size. The shaft of the turbine has been modelled as a rigid one mass with no friction, [9]. The electronic converter has been modelled as a lossless voltage source, which sets the rotor voltage. Rotor voltage is controlled by two PI controllers [7], one for each dq coordinate, which control the active and reactive power generated by the wind turbine. And finally, an aerodynamic subsystem has been laid out that takes as an input the wind speed and the angular speed of the hub and outputs the torque applied to the shaft [7]. Rearranging the equations for the 5th order model yields the expressions (1), (2) and (3).

$$\begin{cases} \dot{X}_1(t) = f_1(X(t), U(t)) \\ \dot{X}_2(t) = f_2(X(t), U(t)) \\ \dots \\ \dot{X}_n(t) = f_n(X(t), U(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$X(t) = [\varphi_{sd}, \varphi_{sq}, \varphi_{rd}, \varphi_{rq}, \omega, PID_{vd}, PID_{vq}]^T \quad (2)$$

$$U(t) = [u_{sd}, u_{sq}, Q, v_{wind}]^T \quad (3)$$

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Where $X(t)$ is the state variables vector and $U(t)$ is the input variables vector, φ_{sd} , φ_{sq} , φ_{rd} , φ_{rq} are the magnetic fluxes of the stator and the rotor expressed in the $dq0$ rotating frame, ω is the rotor speed and PID_{vd} , PID_{vq} are variables that hold the internal state of each PI rotor voltage controller. u_{sd} and u_{sq} are the stator voltages expressed in the $dq0$ frame of reference, Q is the ideal reactive power generation and v_{wind} is the wind speed. For the 3rd order model, φ_{sd} , φ_{sq} are not state variables, they are expressed in terms of the rotor fluxes.

3. Linearization

The model of the wind turbine presented in Section 2 is time invariant but non-linear. In order to transform it to a LTI system, a linearization must be carried out. The linearization techniques used in this work have been adapted from [10].

The first step is to reduce the set of equations presented in Section 2 to a system of explicit Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE). The system is linearized around an equilibrium point and expressed as a State-Space system. State variables and inputs are expressed in terms of the equilibrium point, as shown in (4), (5) and (6). To obtain the final values of the state, intermediate steps are unbiased using this equilibrium point.

$$\Delta \dot{X}(t) = A\Delta X(t) + B\Delta U(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta X(t) = X(t) - X_{equilibrium_point} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta U(t) = U(t) - U_{equilibrium_point} \quad (6)$$

To obtain the equilibrium point, (1) must be solved taking into account all derivatives are equal to zero. There is no analytical solution for this system. Hence, numerical approaches, such as the Newton-Raphson method is used to calculate the equilibrium point. The major shortcomings of these methods are their reliability heavily depending on the starting guess. One way to simplify this problem is to convert it to an equivalent system of equations with less unknown variables. To transform the multivariable system of equations to a single variable system, we propose the following algorithm:

1. The equation whose differential term is the angular speed of the rotor was removed.
2. Remaining differential terms in the system were zeroed and the equations were solved analytically treating the rotor speed as a constant.

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3. The analytical expressions obtained previously were substituted back in the differential equation of the rotor speed.
4. The result is a system with one equation, and one unknown variable, the rotor speed. Newton-Raphson method was setting the initial guess as 1.0, for per-unit magnitudes were used and simulations carried out begin start with the wind turbine generating power.
5. Once the rotor speed in the equilibrium point is obtained, substituting it in the analytical expressions of the other state variables yields the equilibrium point.

The method of Heun [11] is used to compute the values of the states in the next time step. It works by first computing the derivate of the current values in the time step t , using the method of Euler [11] to find out the next variable values in the $t+1$ instant and finding out the derivative of the state functions in that instant. The final value of the states is calculated with the average of the derivatives both in t and $t+1$.

4. MATLAB-Simulink implementation

MATLAB-Simulink block diagrams are used to simulate the non-linear and linearized models, both 5th and 3rd order. For the linearized models, simulations in parallel were also carried out. The linearized model includes the operations to express the initial state and the inputs in terms of the equilibrium point and calculating the final value of the states.

These models have not been simulated directly using MATLAB user interface, but within a script. This script reads the wind input data, the parameters of the wind turbine, and computes the expression of the matrices used in the linearized models. It executes the simulation and then measures the time elapsed for each simulation during each mode of simulation.

To implement serial simulation of a certain number of wind turbines, a simple loop has been used. For implementing the parallel resolution methods, the `parfor` instruction has been used. MATLAB implements parallel computing by spawning as many instances as cores the machine has. To prevent high startup times, a dummy `parfor` was instated at the beginning of the script.

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5. C++ Implementation

An implementation in C++ to simulate the linearized models has been developed in order to be compared against the CUDA solver. This implementation also performs auxiliary tasks needed by CUDA such as file input/output or error handling. Analytical expressions of the state space matrices obtained in Section 3 were automatically converted to C++ code using the MATLAB function `c_code`. Previous to the solver, the value of both matrices are computed for the specified equilibrium point. The algorithm of the solver can be summarized as shown in Figure 2. The optimization flags used to compile all C++ code with GCC compiler were:

```
-O2 -march=native -mtune=native -funroll-loops --fast-math
```

```
forEach component i in ΔX: //Compute the initial value of the solver
    ΔXi= Xinitial,i-Xequilibrium_point,i
//Precalculate the input values in terms of the equilibrium point for each
time point
forEach U in U(t)
    forEach component i in U(t)
        ΔU(t)i=U(t)i-Uequilibrium_point,i

t=0 //t is the current time
//if the simulation time has not been reached, continue calculating
while t<=tend
    //Calculate the values of the state for the output by removing the bias
    forEach component i in X(t)
        X(t)i= ΔXi + Xequilibrium_point,i

    //Calculate the next state using Euler's method.
    //First, Calculate the derivate of the state and store it on ΔXprime
    ΔXprime_Euler=0
    //Perform Matrix-Multiplication using 2 nested loops. Previous to this
operation, the ΔXprime vector is not zeroed. Therefore, ΔXprime = A·ΔX+ B·ΔU(t)
    Matrix_Multiply(A, ΔX, ΔXprime_Euler)
    Matrix_Multiply(B, ΔU(t), ΔXprime_Euler)

    //Calculate the value of the State for t+1 using Euler's method as an
intermediate step for Heun's method.
    forEach component i in X(t)
        ΔXEuler,i= ΔXi + h*ΔXprime_Euler,i //h is the integration step

    //Calculate the derivate in t+1 and store in the temporary variable ΔXprime_Heun
    ΔXprime_Heun=0
    Matrix_Multiply(A, ΔXEuler, ΔXprime_Heun)
    Matrix_Multiply(B, ΔU(t+1), ΔXprime_Heun)

    forEach component i in X(t) //Update the State by averaging both derivatives
        ΔXi= ΔXi + h*(ΔXprime_Heun,i + ΔXprime_Euler,i)/2

    t = t + h //Update the current time with the integration step
```

Figure 2. Pseudocode of state-space integrator in C++

6. CUDA Implementation

CUDA is an architecture of parallel computing that uses the large computing power of the GPU to proportionate an extraordinary performance boost for general-purpose calculations. CUDA embeds itself in C++ code, by extending its syntax and providing an API that allows interfacing with the graphics unit, memory copying and other auxiliary functions. CUDA code is written alongside C++ code, in functions called kernels. Calling the kernel from C++ code that is executed in the host machine, is similar to calling a C++ function, it follows the same syntax with some additions. Each kernel spawns some threads which execute the same kernel, while this threads are grouped into blocks, which share memory and allow for synchronization among threads.

The fundamental operation of the CUDA kernel is the multiplication of a matrix by a vector. The cornerstone of the optimized kernel is optimizing this operation. In [12], several kernels were studied which implemented different algorithms. The largest matrix used in this paper will be 7×7 in size. The best kernel for integrating any matrix whose dimension is less than 7×7 is the one where each thread processes each row of the matrix. For this reason, the kernel used for this implementation will process one thread per row. On block-level layout, it was determined that each block should integrate 32 models at the same time. Higher occupancy and lack of thread divergence were the reasons for choosing that number [13]. Threads of each block were assigned in an interleaved way to ensure optimal memory access.

The workflow of the kernel proposed in this paper is divided in three stages:

- **Host-to-Device memory copy:** As input values, only a copy of the stator voltages and the reactive power of reference were sent. But for the wind speed, N vectors of contiguous vectors were sent to the GPU's global memory [13].
- **Kernel execution:** Once all data has been sent, the kernel is executed. Figure 3 details the pseudocode of this kernel. All dimensions of the vectors are passed as constants, which allows the loops to be unrolled and the conditional branches to be resolved at compile time [13]. The section of the loop is substituted by a set of independent alternating multiplications and additions. The GPU processor can exploit this fact by using Instruction Level Parallelism (ILP) [13].
- **Device-to-Host memory copy:** This stage happens simultaneously with the kernel execution. A special memory called Zero-copy memory was created on the host that allows direct communication from the graphic card to store data on the RAM [13].

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```

//i is the current component of the vector of states and inputs being processed.
current_model,i =Get_current_model_and_component()

 $\Delta X_i = X_{initial,i} - X_{equilibrium\_point,i}$  //Compute the initial value of the solver
t=0 //t is the current time

synchronize //Synchronize all threads within current block
//To prevent slow memory reading, the value of the corresponding input vector
of the instant t+1 is cached in shared memory. This memory can be accessed by
all threads while being efficient [13].
//In the next iteration, U(t) will be equal to that previous value, and they
are simply read from the block's internal memroy.

read U(0)i and store in shared memory Unext,i
Unext,i = Unext,i - Uequilibrium\_point,i

//if the simulation time has not been reached, continue calculating
while t<=tend
    if i < number_inputs //The number of states is 5 or 7 whereas the number of
inputs is 4.
        //Swap the value of U(t+1) from the previous iteration in U(t) for this
operation
        Ucurrent,i = Unext,i // Ucurrent,i is also in shared memory
        //Read the value of the input in the next time point
        read U(t+1)i and store in shared memory Unext,i
        Unext,i = Unext,i - Uequilibrium\_point,i

    synchronize //It must be ensured that all threads have read their
corresponding Ucurrent,i and Unext,i

    //Calculate the output values and store the result in Zero-Copy memory.
    write in Zero-Copy memory X(t)i=  $\Delta X_i + X_{equilibrium\_point,i}$ 

    //Calculate Next Step according to Euler's method
    //Each CUDA thread calculates the sum of 2 scalar products Ai-row· $\Delta X$  + Bi-row·U.
Two temporary variables have been created, which will hold the values of the
two scalar products. Doing so allows the use of ILP
    Vartemp_1=0
    Vartemp_2=0
    for j=1 to number_states
        Vartemp_1 += Ai,j· $\Delta X_j$ 
        if j<number_inputs //Not all threads will correspond to an input vector
component, due to number_states > number_inputs
            Vartemp_2= Vartemp_2+ Bi,j· $\Delta U_{current,j}$ 
        end
    Xprime_Euler= h*(Vartemp_1 + Vartemp_2) // Vartemp_1 + Vartemp_2 is the derivative
of the state's function in instant t. h is the integration step
     $\Delta X_{Euler,i} = \Delta X_i + X_{prime\_Euler}$  //Get the value of the state vector for t+1 using
Euler's method

    synchronize //It must be ensured that all threads have calculated its
corresponding  $\Delta X_{Euler,i}$ 

```

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```
//Calculate the derivative in t+1 using the interleaved loop, again
Vartemp_1=0
Vartemp_2=0
for j=1 to number_states
    Vartemp_1= Vartemp_1+ Ai,j*ΔXj
    if j<number_inputs
        Vartemp_2= Vartemp_2+ Bi,j*ΔUnext,j
end
//Update state and the current simulation time, Using Heun's method
ΔXi= ΔXi + (h*(Vartemp_1 + Vartemp_2) + Xtemp,i)/2
t = t + h //Update current time
```

Figure 3. Pseudocode of the CUDA kernel solver

7. Results

To test the performance of each solver, a 2 MW wind turbine subject to a voltage dip (a voltage dips is a short-term voltage decrease, [14]) has been simulated. For more detailed information about the parameters of the wind turbine can be checked [7]. The time span simulated is 10 s with a time step of 250 μs. The number of wind turbines simulated has been varied from 1 to 500. All tests conducted were carried out in a 64-bits *Intel® Core™ i5 CPU at 2,67 GHz* CPU with 4 GB of RAM. The operating system used was *Xubuntu-16.04-desktop-amd64*. Simulink simulations were carried out using *MATLAB R2015A*. The software used to compile the C++ implementation was *G++ version 5.3.1*. For the CUDA implementation, a NVIDIA GTX 960 card was used with a *CUDA* runtime whose version is 7.5.

Figure 4 graphs the computing cost of each implementation considered. CUDA implementation is the faster one when a large amount of wind turbines is simulated. The differences in performance reach a limit. Table I summarizes the computational cost for the C++ and CUDA implementations for the 5th and 3rd order model, measured in seconds. For the C++ version, it has been measured the computational cost of the function described in Figure 2. For the CUDA kernel, it has been measured the time need to execute the kernel and complete both data transfers.

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Figure 4. Computational cost of wind turbine simulation relative to CUDA time

Table I. Computational cost of wind turbine simulation relative to CUDA for the 5th and 3rd order model

N° Wind turbines	5 th order		3 rd order	
	C++ (s)	CUDA (s)	C++ (s)	CUDA (s)
1	0,0038	0,0235	0,0026	0,0123
2	0,0074	0,0239	0,0052	0,0218
5	0,0180	0,0271	0,0127	0,0250
10	0,0358	0,0302	0,0243	0,0284
20	0,0714	0,0314	0,047	0,0298
50	0,179	0,0326	0,117	0,0310
100	0,356	0,0338	0,236	0,0322
200	0,711	0,0462	0,469	0,0347
500	1,79	0,106	1,17	0,0800

In Figure 5, it is shown the computational time of each stage in the CUDA implementation for the 3rd order and 5th order linearized models. Due to the layout of the memory, the maximum performance during the copying stage from device-to-host is for a certain number of wind turbines which is multiple of 32. It can also be observed how data transfer is the operation which takes the mayor time of the computation and this conditioned the total time consumed by the implementation. According to the specifications of the machine where it was simulated, the maximum transfer speed is about 6 GB/s with the kernel achieving 98% of that speed.

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Figure 5. Computational cost of CUDA implementation by stages

8. Conclusions

In this paper, a wind turbine model has been implemented in MATLAB/Simulink, C++ and CUDA for computational cost comparison purposes. Results have proven that the CUDA kernel implementation is the most efficient architecture when a large number of wind turbine models are simulated. That characteristic could allow to simulate entire wind farms without compromising the detail level of simulation of individual wind turbine, as happens when aggregation techniques are applied. During simulation, data transfer from device to host is carried out in parallel with the execution of the kernel to increase the performance. The bottleneck of the CUDA kernel is this data transfer, that is more significant the more wind turbines are simulated. As the data transfer bandwidth has been maxed out, no further improvements in the kernel will make a difference in performance. Hardware upgrades are needed to increase simulation speed.

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